

Information Technology as a Mechanism for Educational Transformations in a Changing Society

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Suggested Citation

Egete, D.O., Ele, B.I. & Njama-Abang, O. (2023). Information Technology as a Mechanism for Educational Transformations in a Changing Society. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(4), 565-573.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).51](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).51)

Abstract:

Education is a definite and ground-breaking channel for a high standard of living, an opportunity for intellectual interactions, social networking amongst current academic professionals, college and university graduates, at local, state, and community. The primary purpose of life-long education is to promote personal and professional development, and advancement of the national and world economy. Ancient times support the premise that after continued self-regulating attempts, the time has come for current and future graduates, professionals, and the entire education community to focus on the primacy of computer information

technology, which has widened human access to vital data, video, and information transmission and communication, also created an irreversible phenomenon in instruction and learning endeavors, and continues to serve as the best medium for multiple sources of information and communication. The emergence of computer information technology has equally created a wide range of opportunities for greater production; doing away with the lingering global language barriers, and creating a working podium in the academic and political world. It is a proven tenet that the continued use of computer information technology and associated devices such as the Internet, mobile telephones, and electronic mail for data, information transmission, and communication has improved the standard of living and enhanced the exchange of ideas, effective method of learning endeavours, a decrease in alarming attrition rate of students dropping out of the degree programmes and improvement in academic performance.

Keywords: *information technology, mechanism, educational transformation, changing society, academic performance, scientific research.*

Introduction

Education is a noble channel for misplaced potential; a life-long education is a noble journey of inheritance for everyone. Prior to the development of computer information technology (CIT), family structure varied from

one location to another environment, Barnes and Janet (2012), Lynch (2000), and Toffler (1980) noted that the wave of agriculture tended to sway and inspired individuals to live in large, and multigenerational households venue with uncles, aunts, in-laws, grandparents and cousins,

and all of them resided under the same roof, worked collectively as an economic, productive and united family. Notably, the current economic situation has shifted the family composition from field manual labor to factory activities, and family units get interrupted, and can no longer function together as unified family units. The once-upon-a-time united family units are now confronted with relocation from one village, state, and nation to another village, state, and country. Bednar (2005), Hanushek (2007), Keengwe (2007), and Toffler (1980) assert that the education of children had been turned over to schools, colleges, and universities, and caring for elderly parents and relatives to hospitals, nursing homes, and associated healthcare facilities with limited family participation in those early days, that is before colonialism. Social events were stored in human brains, and tribal leaders, elderly wise men, priests, ministers, and parents carried these brilliant and notable memories with them in the form of history, myth, wisdom, and narratives, legends were transmitted to children through Speech, song, poetry, and chant (Toffler, 1980. Roszak (1986). Esin, 1991. and Ayers, 2004). The development of computer information technology has shattered the memory barrier and transferred social memories outside of human brains beyond their previous environment.

The arrival of computer information technology into the education community and human society has accelerated and re-energized the unconventional culture of communication, documentation, instruction, and learning endeavors; thereby, creating a noble channel for misplaced potential (Esin 2011, 2013 and 1991). According to Clinton (1996), Goldstone (2013), Klopfer, Osterweil, Groff, and Haas (2009), the new computer information technology idea is structured to equip current and future graduates with the ability to endure associated human humiliations, frustrations, setbacks, and inadequate financial support. However, this life-long and enduring education is a lasting investment that can contribute to the growth and development of students, and educational leaders, and the improvement of a creative, inventive, and resourceful society. Leonard

(1968), Leamson (1999), and Partee (2002) asserted that long-lasting education is a deep-seated and convincing corridor for social progress and growth, advancement, and a benchmark for global economic advancement.

International Organization of Scientific Research

Education is an original and ground-breaking medium to effective and productive standard of living; in fact, such a process must involve social and intellectual interactions amongst students, professors, educators and members of the community. Times to supports the premise that after continued self-regulating attempts the time has come for current and future graduates, professors, associated educators, and the entire education community to focus on the primacy of computer information technology. The emergence of computer information technology has widened human access to fundamental information, created irreversible phenomena in education endeavors, and continues to serve as the best medium for multiple data, voice, and information transmission, learning, and communication. Furthermore, CIT has equally produced a wide range of opportunities for greater production, the annihilation of the protracted global language barriers, creation a better working platform for current and future college and university graduates and world leaders.

Leaders are made, and not born. There cannot be dedicated leaders without a legion of impartial and understandable followers, and nobody should expect loyal followers without commitment, dedication and determined endeavors to lead the most complex human kingdom. The human mind is a replica of a blank sheet of paper that is governed by unconscious, natural feelings. Morley (2013), Hanushek and Rivkin (2007), and Esin (2014) asserted that graduates of today's educational system are the captive audience who are confronted with an uncertain workforce, financial uncertainty, and worldwide political improprieties. To minimize the degree of the apparent human misdeed and pretense, college graduates. Professors,

associated educators, and society at large must embrace the education process as a promised pathway for acquiring appropriate skills, knowledge, proper conduct, morals, and development of life-long expertise, attainment of a healthy, physical, mental, financial, economic, and compatible standard of living. The major purpose of computer information technology in education settings is to equip individuals, college and university graduates, and society with unlimited latitude for important potentials, dignified standards of living, the liberation of the human mind, articulation of intellectual, mission-driven talent, and a stable contribution to the attainment of economic growth and citizenship.

Current education researchers such as Brouillette (2000), Ayers (2004), Henrickson (2007), and Rothstein and Adams (2009) admit that one of the convincing and credible codes of adjustment must involve academic professors, associated educators, and higher education administrator's willingness to amplify the culture of effective management, securing the cooperation of the recipients (current and future graduates) by holding fast to the stated measures, reconnecting with the mission, philosophy and historic commitment and dedication and willingness to mentor, nurture and prepare the current generation with adequate skills and expertise for the workforce and citizenship.

Partee (2003) and Wirth and Perkins (2008) noted that an enduring education must be viewed as a sturdy reorganization, transformation, and potential for the lasting, unified, and believable conduit to evoke the misplaced educational potentials. Nothing in this life is too big or too small unless by comparison; therefore, current and future college and university graduates must vigorously learn "to crawl" to arrive at the educational Promised Land. It will be considered a naive concept for tertiary graduates to look forward to the attainment of enduring educational freedom and liberty without individual responsibility; hence, I openly encourage the graduates and would-be college and university graduates to take full control of their academic pilgrimage, redirect their educational posture from the economic

wasteland, and reconnect with the educational promised land. The current college and university graduates must accept the fact that the educational system is a fundamental and lasting fertile rotating garden, and in a few months, or years, most of them will be selected to serve as educators, professors, vice-chancellors, presidents, prime ministers and in an allied capacity in the educational system and the world community.

Esin (2014) in his studies on a balanced salary structure for academic professors and associated educators as a pathway to quality education noted that large segments of the world community view computer information technology as a productive skill, while professors and associated educators see computer information technology as an added value to their already demanding, arduous, and almost impossible academic workload. Jaschik (2006) in his studies on eroding faculty paychecks further asserted that to establish a unified and well-structured educated populace, collaborative, measurable, and education-driven goals must be implemented with emphasis on how to promote integration and opportunity for academic professors, allied educators, and the large segment of the community to work collectively. A lasting and life-long education does not operate in a vacuum, but in a multipart framework that must include the unconditional participation of professors, allied educators, parents, and state, national, and local community representatives. Ayers (2004), Henrickson (2007), Samkang-Zeeb and Blettner (2009), Hearn (2010), Stair Reynolds (2014), and Esin (2013) contend that an enduring education; precisely, the one that is built on effective use of computer information technology for communication, instruction, and learning process, must extend its loop beyond the regular classroom sessions through open access to professional mentorship, nurturing, academic advisement, skilled computer information technology training on emerging computer, software, and associated peripherals.

The Dominance of Computer Information Technology

Computer information technology (CIT) presents the foundation of a unified and believable corridor for reorganization, transformation, and recalling past and current events, including opportunities for productive and creative human potential. CIT is a promising medium for acquiring an enduring and suitable standard of living, lifetime expertise, and the attainment of good health, mental, and financial. Economic and social development, beyond every reasonable doubt, the evolution of CIT has contributed immeasurably to the development of a free world of resourceful and economic stability. The conventional wisdom supports the premise that the culture of lifetime education begins from nativity to maturity and the successful implementation of CIT classrooms for instruction is extremely imperative. The world community cannot afford stable educational systems and resourceful human society without the unconditional commitment of providers (professors and associated educators), recipients (students), and the entire education enterprise (Sutphin 1987, 2009, Samkang-Zeeb & Blettner 2009 and Kroenke, 2010). Parents, community representatives, academic professors, and allied educators must be empowered with wide-range professional development in the use of computer information technology to nurture, mentor, and unleash the infinite potential in the current and future graduates, known as imminent education leaders.

Stakeholders in education are therefore informed to provide a suitable and satisfactory landing ground, a long-term solution, and an added value to accept, acknowledge, recognize, and prepare the large promising segments of college and university graduates to emerge as enlightened and highly CIT experts of the unified global education. The world community views professors and allied educators as endowed, scholastic, intelligent, and civilized citizens of the free and unified human society. On this radiance, Henrickson (2007), Samkang-Zeeb (2009), and Ayers (2004) asserted that

current and future graduates, under the umbrella of academic elites, must be viewed as resolute, and tenacious academic brigades with continued determination to search for available educational opportunities. Furthermore, college and university graduates must be strongly encouraged to fulfill their educational dreams through the development of self-confidence, and the expertise to make intelligent decisions and recognize paths that lead to success. Computer information technology has permeated the education systems and society and failure to effectively implement computer information technology to empower the world's future education leaders with CIT skills will be a regrettable mistake. It is a proven tenet that the implementation of computer information technology and associated devices such as the Internet, mobile telephones, and electronic mail for data, video, information transmission, and communication has improved the standard of living and enhanced the exchange of ideas, effective method of instruction, academic performance and credible techniques thereby, bridging the gap between language barriers and learning endeavors.

The development of computer information technology in the educational setting, according to Oden and Kelly (2007), Samkang-Zeeb (2009), Morley (2013) Stair and Reynolds (2014), has expanded our human capacity to cope with the challenges of managing and delivering instruction in different subject areas. Partee, (2002) and Morley (2013), in accord with current education researchers, asserted that the emergence of computer information technology into the educational system has created a tool for academic professors and associated educators to successfully manage and deliver instruction to geographically diverse segments of the community, communicate with a wide range of audience, and widen the scope of information flow, and quality of the educational resources to schools, college and university communities. Indeed, this influx of computer information technology into the education community and human society has inevitably accomplished more than information flow; it has equally rendered the delivery of instruction and learning

endeavors more flexible, attractive, and challenging to a larger audience of learners.

Computer information technology is sponsoring a remarkable social, economic, and global transformation: as a consequence, extensive expertise in computer information technology is critical for employment opportunities for current and future graduates, and the economic development of human communities. There is a collaboration between learning and action, and the talent to learn is the beginning of action, wisdom and knowledge, understanding, and the awareness of individual potential. In this regard, computer information technology, according to Henrickson (2007) and Samkang-Zeeb (2009) is indeed an indispensable component for excellent communication and instructional problem-solving. Acquisition of new skills and knowledge is a of individual reasoning and such knowledge and reasoning process must be rooted in the right soil. The framework of computer information technology is in fact, a call to battle global language barriers, communication obstacles, and inequitable access to data, information, and records, and a catalyst of self-transformation that leads to the transformation of education communities.

CIT has become the most powerful, excellent innovative mechanism for educational progress, and has also set a stage for the expansion of an individual's intellectual capability and awareness of how to fully utilize information technology to press forward for personal and professional education transformation. Before the influx of computer information systems into the education system, the majority of human activities were once done manually and with tasking effort. Today, human society and the educational community have changed dramatically with the infusion of computer information technology and associated devices. Indeed, CIT has penetrated almost every aspect of day-to-day operations, educational settings, and business environments. Change is a dynamic channel for growth and development. Education is the true wealth of every nation and community. Computer information technology is the hope for the future and is considered a sensory organ by creating greater accuracy,

precision, and better information flow which has impacted the advancement of communication mediums (Oz 2009, Samkange- Zeeb and Blettner 2009, and Hearn (2010).

Furthermore, CIT has improved a wide range of interpersonal contact through mobile phones, the Internet, and electronic mail systems. Undeniably, computer information technology is on the threshold of putting innovative and skill-oriented expertise into the educational system. Consequently, this emphasis

Must attract and engage substantial financial investment in computer information technology infrastructure and professional training to support the modern workforce, and social well-being of college and university graduates, who are also the future world leaders. Henrickson (2007), Samkang-Zeeb (2009), and Ayers (2004) noted that CIT has precipitated and accelerated the use of the internet, mobile telephones, and electronic mail and transformed the world community into a comfortable monarchy enabling individuals in the most isolated parts of the globe to be contacted any time and at all times. The use of CIT and associated devices such as the internet, mobile telephones, voice over IP, (Vol P), - phones, and electronic mail for communication has improved the standard of living and enhanced the exchange of ideas, effective instruction, and learning process. Moore (1996) and Partee (2002) stated that CIT has made electronic interactions and online education simple enough for students to stay off-campus, completely outside the traditional college and universities framework, and still select the program of study, complete class projects, class assignments, and the degree program on scheduled time and date. Sutphin (1987), Oz (2009), Samkange-Zeeb and Blettner (2009) noted that the incorporation of computer information technology into the education settings and workforce has opened, enhanced, and increased the ocean of research competence, individual development, national income, global education partnership, and world economic stability.

The majority of college and university campuses have increased the thresholds of

communication, data and voice transmission, instruction, and learning from remote locations without any restriction. The advancement of computer information technology in the educational enterprise has revolutionized the world community; therefore, the importance and all-inclusive advantages of computer information technology in every sphere of life and education settings must not be taken for granted. Hanushek and Rivkin (2007) and Vermaat (2014) asserted that online distance education has given new opportunities to students by offering facilities for learners to prepare, save, edit, store, generate the printout of standard documents, and submit class projects, homework assignment, and communicate online with professors. It follows that when computer information technology is incorporated into the academic process it will help to prepare and liberate inventive students, professors, allied educators, and resourceful citizens out of the fragile human environment. A majority of education researchers such as Samkange-Zeeb & Blettner (2009) and Kroenke (2010) support the premise that computer information technology is a credible corridor that contributes to the growth and stabilization of prudent individuals, and the education of the community, and help to decrease the alarming rate of students dropping out of the degree programs. In the past, the use of textbooks was fundamental and a domineering channel for instruction and learning, and colleges and universities were judged by the volume of books in their libraries. Today, the influx of computer information technology and associated devices in the education community for administrative duties, the Internet, electronic mail, distance education, online libraries, and immediate access to a variety of learning resources has outdistanced the total reliance on textbooks for instruction on college and university campuses. Schofield (1995), Henrickson (2007), Wirth and Perkins (2008) and Samkang-Zeeb (2009) Ayers (2004) asserted that although the culture of distance education and immediate access to information and learning resources on the Internet is, Some extent, an inadequate replacement of the human desire to interact and learn with colleagues, cohorts, and friends in the

traditional classroom settings, study halls, and libraries, CIT has come with its immeasurable advantages that far outweigh those of traditional education, Indeed. CIT falls in line with the march of time.

Thomas (1996), Partee (2000), and Goldstone (2013) noted that the use of computer information technology for online distance education process has amplified new challenging opportunities for learners with inadequate financial sponsorship, unforeseen circumstances, individual disability, travel expenses, and physical distance to complete their degree program in reasonable learning pace from the comfort of the home. Computer information technology is dominating the world community with a clear mission of transforming the educational process, the individual, and human society into a free-language-barrier kingdom. The world community has emerged from traditional chalkboard to electronic bulletin board, electronic learning, (e-learning), and Virtual Learning Environment System (VLES) that enables individuals to have access to online instructional materials and resources; thereby, creating an ocean of guaranteed progress and development of the educational community.

A majority of colleges and universities are responding aggressively to the use of computer information technology to manage and deliver instruction in the classroom. CIT has also created opportunities for phenomenal adjustment to instruction and learning endeavors and unparalleled benchmarks on how to measure professors' and learners' outcomes. Oz (2009), Samkange-Zeeb & Blettner (2009) and Vermaat (2014) noted that computer information technology has extended its tentacle to assist most private and public corporations in reevaluating, and streamlining their business policies and procedures: therefore, the entire education system, especially the college and university communities, must equally be willing and ready to embrace the education reform that will certainly help in the reorganization of instruction and learning endeavors, day-to-day human activities, and citizenship. Today, colleges and universities are breathing in the era of rapid increase of computer information

technology, and associated devices. Its growth and advancement, that has revolutionized and provided a vehicle for unquenchable human interactions, distance learning, and intellectual communication.

Sutphin (1987), Partee (2003), Oz (2009), Samkange-Zeeb and Blettner (2009), Esin (2013), and Vermaat (2014) noted that the advantages of computer information technology on college and university campuses are myriad; for example, the connection to the shared network, shared printer, and a central database for instruction and learning and access to vital records can help to streamline the administrative activities, reduce the cost of acquiring separate standalone printers for production and management of sensitive records. The immediate access to student information, according to Esin (2011) and Partee (2003), will help to decrease the echelon of negligence on the part of graduating and transfer students who will advertently or inadvertently show up for scheduled appointments in the chancellor, vice chancellor, chief librarian, and academic advisors offices without any document to validate their outstanding balance, unreturned library materials, and with outdated transcripts, and out-of-date degree plans.

Conclusion

Lifetime education, which comes in different forms and through multiple channels, is the foundation of humanity. In this regard, computers and their related apparatus have come to enhance and solidify this foundation by creating a storage house for knowledge. Indeed, computer information technology is the premier pathway for effective electronic data, voice and information transmission, communication, inquiry, and ongoing investigation of knowledge and facts. Successful implementation of computer information technology will provide opportunities for users to share central network file servers, and network printers and will also enable higher education administrators, professors, allied educators, staff, designated personnel, and academic advisors to have immediate access to student information stored

in the institution's central file servers. The expertise in all fields of academic disciplines and human endeavors is an open-ended journey. It is my line of reasoning that education, technology, instruction, and learning are very difficult undertakings, but the rewards are undeniable, reliable, steady, and endless. It is worth noting that the power of education, will certainly contribute to nation-building, personal and professional advancement, and sustainable economic success must extend beyond completing the loop of ordinary development of job skills. We thus, profess that this current achievement could have not been possible without the evolution of computer information technology. Conventional wisdom supports the premise that computer information technology has permeated the educational system and society and rendered our society immeasurable advantages that far outweigh those of traditional education, it falls in line with the march of time.

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